

CYBER SECURITY MACRO TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT DIRECTIONS OF THE CYBER SECURITY INDUSTRY

Huseynzade G.

MBA student of Azerbaijan Technical University

ABSTRACT

Today, rapid developments in the field of information and communication technologies are considered as an element that creates the basis for social and economic development. It is clear that the transformation taking place in the digital world is parallel to the increase in the welfare of citizens. However, it is recognized that cyber security and its development are seen as an integral and indivisible part of this transformation. It is clear that there is a principle of direct causality between the development of information technologies and the illegal and harmful use of these technologies. To counter this, cyber security is increasingly on the agenda of decision-making bodies in more and more countries. In this study, we examine the examples of cyber security clusters created around the world by developing the cyber security ecosystem in our country. We propose to create a cyber security cluster in our country along with the skills needed for these clusters.

Keywords: Cyber security, trends, cyber security industry, Information and communication technology, networks.

Information and communication technology networks, devices and services are becoming more important day by day. In 2016, almost half of the world's population used the Internet (3.5 billion users). According to a study, it is estimated that by 2020 there will be more than 12 billion devices connected to the Internet. According to another statistic from 2016, almost one percent of all emails sent were malicious attacks [5]. This is the highest indicator of recent years.

Ransomware attacks are increasing day by day. According to cyber security experts, the number of these attacks increased by 118% in the first half of 2019 alone. Ransomware is a type of virus that encrypts data and prevents users from accessing data until they pay a ransom to the malicious person to unlock it. Its attacks are increasingly affecting businesses and consumers. The average ransom demand from attackers exceeded \$1,000 in 2016. The WannaCry attack in May 2017 caused major disruptions to companies and hospitals in more than 150 countries. This worldwide cyber attack targeted computers running Microsoft Windows operating system, encrypted data and demanded ransom payments in Bitcoin cryptocurrency.

With the growth of information technology, these technologies have become illegal. It is clear that there is a principle of direct causality between the development of information technologies and the illegal and harmful use of these technologies. In order to eliminate this effect, cyber security is more prominent on the agenda of decision-making bodies of countries. For this purpose, doctrines and strategies related to cyber security of countries are becoming more important day by day. However, there is a noticeable gap and disorganization among stakeholders in the country in terms of the ability to provide appropriate strategies, capabilities and programs to ensure the safe use of information and communication technologies.

Cybersecurity has always been a never-ending race, but the pace of change is accelerating. Companies continue to invest in technology to drive their businesses. They are now deploying more systems into their IT networks to support remote work, improve customer

experience and create value, creating potential new vulnerabilities.

At the same time, adversaries – no longer limited to individual actors – include high-end organizations using tools and capabilities integrated with artificial intelligence and machine learning. The scope of the threat is growing and no organization is immune to it. Small and medium-sized businesses, municipalities, state and federal governments face such risks along with large companies. Even today's most sophisticated cyber controls, however effective, will soon become obsolete.

Cyber security macro trends. With the development of technology, the term "Cyber Security" has entered our lives. The fact that there are those who use technology for evil as well as those who use it for good has given rise to this term. In short, cyber security is a program designed to protect networks and databases from computers to mobile devices, from servers to electronic systems. It is applied to ensure some kind of information security.

Cyber attacks are actually increasing with the evolution of modern technologies and the digital transformation of the world. Cybercriminals can access and disclose your personal information, or even shut down your entire business operations by exposing confidential information. Facebook, Dominos, Microsoft, etc. is a victim of such cyber-attacks and to deal with these attacks you need to keep a close eye on emerging trends in cyber security.

Especially since 2020, the global pandemic has led to an increase in cybercrime cases. The reason for this is very simple. Home Office! The home office has become a way of working that most companies are turning to due to the pandemic. This situation was most useful for spies. Companies have been observed to be more vulnerable to malicious attacks.

As hackers and security providers race to destroy each other, cybersecurity remains an industry that never stops working. New threats and innovative ways to combat them are constantly emerging. In this document, we will take a look at the latest cyber security trends for 2022. "Cyber Security Trends" are listed in 10 articles as follows:

Cybersecurity risks associated with remote working. Due to Covid-19, many organizations and companies had to move their employees to remote work quite quickly. Many surveys show that most employees continue to work remotely even after the pandemic. Working from home naturally presents new cybersecurity risks, and it's one of the hottest trends in cybersecurity right now. The level of protection in home offices is much lower than in central offices, where security measures such as firewalls, routers and access control are implemented by IT security teams. Traditional security surveys, rushed to avoid disrupting workflow, may not be as successful as they used to be in detecting the new tactics cybercriminals are adopting [1].

Many employees use their personal devices for two-factor authentication, and these devices may also include mobile software versions of instant messaging clients such as Microsoft Teams and Zoom. This blurring of boundaries between personal and professional life increases the risk of sensitive data falling into the wrong hands.

Therefore, it is one of the main cyber security trends that organizations focus on the security issues of distributed workforce. This means identifying and mitigating new vulnerabilities, improving systems, implementing security controls, and ensuring appropriate monitoring and documentation.

The Internet of Things (IoT) is evolving. As the Internet of Things (IoT) expands, more opportunities arise for cybercrime. The Internet of Things is a term used to describe physical devices connected to the Internet that can collect and share data, excluding computers, phones, and servers. Examples of IoT devices are wearable health trackers, smart refrigerators, smart-watches, and voice assistants such as Amazon Echo and Google Home. By 2026, it is estimated that there will be 64 billion IoT devices in operation worldwide. The worldwide trend towards remote working is accelerating this growth.

The increase in the number of devices leads to a change in the dynamics and size of the cyber attack surface. Most IoT devices have less processing and storage capacity than laptops and smartphones. This means that firewalls, antivirus programs, and other security programs become difficult to use. As a result, IoT attacks are among the cyber attack trends to watch out for [2].

Rise of Ransomware. Ransomware is not a new threat. They have been in our lives for almost twenty years, but the threat they pose is constantly increasing. Today, it is estimated that there are more than 120 families of ransomware, and hackers are now quite adept at hiding malicious code. Ransomware is a relatively easy way for hackers to make money, which is partly what drives their growth. Another factor was the Covid-19 pandemic. The rapid digitization of many organizations and the increase in remote working speeds have revealed new targets for ransomware. As a result, both the volume of the attack and the volume of requests increased. In extortion attacks, criminals steal a company's data and encrypt the data so that the company cannot access it. They then blackmail the organization by

threatening to release personal information if the ransom is not paid. Given the sensitive nature of the data in question and the economic burden of paying the ransom, the potential threat posed by this cyber threat is enormous. Ransomware made history in 2020 with the first death related to a cyber attack. In this case, it was not possible to treat patients because the systems of a hospital in Germany were locked [5-9]. The woman, who needed emergency help, was taken to another hospital 30 kilometers away, but it was not possible to save her.

Ransomware attackers are finding more sophisticated methods of phishing attempts thanks to machine learning and more coordinated sharing on the dark web. Hackers often demand payment in hard-to-trace cryptocurrencies. In the coming period, we may see more ransomware attacks against organizations with poor cyber security.

Increasing use of cloud services and threats to cloud security. Vulnerabilities in cloud systems remain one of the biggest trends in the cybersecurity industry. With the rapid and widespread adoption of remote working during the pandemic, the need for cloud-based services and infrastructures has increased significantly, resulting in new security needs for organizations. Cloud services offer a number of advantages such as scalability, efficiency and cost savings. But they are also prime targets for attackers. Misconfigured cloud systems are a major cause of data breaches and unauthorized access, insecure interfaces, and account hacking [6]. The average cost of a data breach is \$3.86 million. That's why it's important for organizations to take steps to minimize cloud threats. In addition to data breaches, network security trends and cloud security challenges facing organizations include:

- Ensuring regulatory compliance in multiple jurisdictions
- Ensuring sufficient IT expertise to meet the demands of cloud computing
- Cloud migration challenges
- Problems with creating more potential entry points for attackers
- Insider threats related to any form of unauthorized remote access, weak passwords, unsecured networks, and accidental or intentional misuse of personal devices

Social engineering attacks are getting smarter. Social engineering attacks such as phishing are not new threats, but are more of a concern today as remote work becomes more common [7]. Attackers target people who connect to their employers' networks from home because they are easier targets. In addition to traditional phishing attacks against employees, we are also seeing an increase in whaling attacks targeting executives.

Smishing attacks (the word phishing is derived from the words "SMS" and "phishing") are used on Whatsapp, Slack, Skype, Signal, Wechat, etc. is also used by and has gained importance due to the popularity of messaging applications. Attackers use these platforms to trick users into downloading malware onto their phones.

Another variation is the "vishing" method, which stands for phone phishing. This method became known in the attack on Twitter in 2020. Hackers posing as IT staff called customer service representatives and convinced them to give them access to an important internal tool. Phone phishing has been used to launch attacks against numerous companies, including financial institutions and large corporations. Also worth mentioning is the SIM theft attack, where fraudsters contact representatives of the customer's mobile operator and convince them that the SIM card has been stolen. After this attack, the phone number must be transferred to another card. If the deception is successful, the cybercriminal gains access to the digital contents of the target's phone.

Organizations are increasing their levels of phishing protection, but criminals are always looking for new ways to stay one step ahead. So much so that there is sophisticated phishing equipment that uses different methods depending on the location of the victims [1] . [3]. Also worth mentioning is the SIM theft attack, where fraudsters contact representatives of the customer's mobile operator and convince them that the SIM card has been stolen. After this attack, the phone number must be transferred to another card. If the deception is successful, the cybercriminal gains access to the digital contents of the target's phone.

Data privacy as a discipline. The rise of data privacy as a discipline in its own right is one of the major data security trends we face today. Numerous high-profile cyberattacks have exposed millions of personally identifiable information (PII) records. This means placing a higher priority on data privacy with the introduction of stricter data laws around the world, such as the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Organizations that fail to comply with regulations and consumer expectations risk fines, a bad reputation and loss of consumer trust. Data privacy is an issue that affects almost all aspects of an organization. As a result, organizations are increasingly focusing on hiring data privacy officers and external assessments to identify areas for improvement such as role-based access control, multi-factor authentication, encryption in transit and at rest, network segmentation, and more. Thus, GDPR provides more consistent protection of personal data of consumers and EU residents. Organizations around the world are gradually changing and restructuring to adapt to the new law.

Improvement of multi-factor authentication. Multi-factor authentication (MFA) is considered the gold standard of authentication. However, malicious people are also finding new ways to bypass these steps with authentication processes via SMS or phone calls. As a result, Microsoft advised users in 2020 to abandon phone-based multi-factor authentication apps and instead use app-based authenticators and security keys.

SMS has some built-in security features, but messages sent for authentication purposes are not encrypted. This means that malicious people can perform espionage attacks between the two ports to obtain OTPs sent in plain text.

This creates a vulnerability for transactions such as online banking, where authentication is typically done via SMS. We're increasingly seeing banks and

other organizations turn to app-based multifactor authentication methods like Google Authenticator and Authy to solve this problem.

The continued rise of artificial intelligence. The number of cyber security threats is too great for humans to handle alone. As a result, organizations are increasingly focusing on artificial intelligence and machine learning to improve their security infrastructure. In this sense, it is also possible to achieve cost savings. Organizations that were damaged by a data breach but had previously fully implemented AI technology earned an average of \$3.58 million in 2020.

Artificial intelligence offers great opportunities in the creation of automated security systems, natural language processing, face detection and automatic threat detection. Artificial intelligence also enables faster analysis of large amounts of risk data [4]. This is useful for both large companies that use large amounts of data, as well as small or medium-sized businesses that may be understaffed in their security teams.

While artificial intelligence offers businesses significant opportunities for stronger threat detection, criminals are also using this technology to automate their attacks using data poisoning and model theft techniques. Development of practical artificial intelligence programs continues. We expect AI and machine learning-driven security tools to continue to grow in sophistication and capability.

Threats to Higher Education. Cybersecurity is among the top priorities of those in the higher education sector, especially during the pandemic, with the rise of online education and remote work. Cybersecurity trends in higher education primarily involve compromised student data. Just this year, three private universities were victims of a cyber attack involving the hacking of student enrollment data (Inside Higher Ed, 2019). With this, stricter security measures were implemented to protect student, teacher and research data in higher education institutions.

Mobile cybersecurity is gaining importance. The popularity of remote work leads to an even greater increase in the number of mobile devices. It has become common for remote workers to switch between different mobile devices, such as tablets and phones, using public Wi-Fi networks and remote collaboration tools. As a result, mobile threats continue to grow and evolve. The introduction of 5G technology has also led to various security vulnerabilities. Patches should be applied immediately when security vulnerabilities are discovered.

Mobile threats include:

- Special spyware designed to infiltrate encrypted messaging apps by spying on them.
- Criminals are looking for ways to exploit critical vulnerabilities in Android devices.
- Mobile malware with a variety of possible application scenarios, from Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks to SMS attacks and data theft.

Mobile cyber security; backend/cloud security is a broad topic that encompasses other aspects such as network security, as well as networks of many connected objects such as wearables and automotive devices (e.g. IoT). There is no single way to protect applications in secure environments. Instead, additional layers of security should be provided to increase the overall level of

security. Security professionals combine mobile software security with hardware-based security solutions to make the storage of sensitive data more secure.

In this era of accelerated digital transformation, cybercriminals are constantly looking for new ways to target and harm individuals and organizations, which means the cybersecurity space will continue to evolve. In order not to be affected by such attacks, it is recommended to regularly monitor emerging trends in cyber security. Using high-quality antivirus software such as Kaspersky Total Security will help you stay safe against the latest cyber threat trends.

In addition to 2022, when cyber security incidents are intense, 2023 will also be full of cyber attacks, and it is emphasized that 6 cyber security predictions for this year will target electric cars in particular, and artificial intelligence-based coding tools will create security gaps:

1. Coding with artificial intelligence tools will create many fundamental vulnerabilities. In the new era, artificial intelligence tools have developed a lot. AI and ML tools can provide written answers, codes for users, generate song lyrics and order your dinner. While this amazing technology excites us, it also brings many security vulnerabilities. Artificial intelligence uses existing computer code to create new algorithms and codes. We predict that the very useful structure of AI and the convenience it provides may create critical security vulnerabilities in the future in an application implemented by a software developer relying on AI coding tools.

2. Attacks against electric cars will increase. The automotive industry is developing day by day and depending on this development, it is undergoing a digital transformation, which includes the emergence of autonomous and electric vehicles with unique safety features, artificial intelligence and electric vehicles, especially in the last 10 years. Cars that were once completely mechanical have become digital devices with millions of lines of code and multiple electronic control units after the digital transformation. Along with the growing demand for electric vehicles, cyber attacks against electric vehicles are predicted to increase worldwide.

3. We will see attacks in the Metaverse more often. Although it has lost its place on the agenda, research on the metaverse universe continues in full swing. We would not be wrong if we say that in the next 10 years we will live in a mixture of real and digital life. While the younger generations can foresee these attacks as they were born in the age of modern technology, older age groups can be quite easy to be fooled. When we wake up to a new day, if we don't want to find our assets in the Metaverse out of place, and if we don't want them to be taken over by a cybercriminal, we will need to take security measures in this area to minimize cyber attacks.

1. Cross-country cyber wars may occur. Cyber attacks are one of the methods used not only by hackers or cybercriminals, but also by large organizations and states. Keeping pace with the digital world continues to

be one of the main tasks of states. The world's largest countries, especially the United States of America, are increasing cyber security measures in all other areas, especially national security. In 2023, it predicts that there is a high probability of interstate cyber war, and the attacks carried out in this direction are expected to continue more and more.

2. Zero trust will be adopted by more companies. Zero trust provides services to protect both infrastructure and data in today's digital transformation. Although many organizations make extensive use of zero trust integration, it is still not enough. In the future, we expect rapid adoption of a zero-trust approach, one of the most fundamental parts of evolving cybersecurity measures that seek to authenticate users wherever possible in modern cloud infrastructure.

3. "Cryptocurrencies will be the target again." Blockchain is a huge technology that integrates all bitcoins and other altcoins. The global economic fluctuations, unemployment and radical decisions made by countries regarding local monetary policies have led to the depreciation of local currencies, while the interest of users in digital currencies, especially bitcoin, has increased. This situation forces ordinary investors who do not fully understand how cryptocurrencies work to enter the cryptocurrency market. Fraudulent activities against this group, which will be the main target of cyber attackers, are predicted to increase significantly. Cryptocurrency markets have been stagnant for a long time, but they have also witnessed attacks where ransom demands are made with digital currencies. we will be Attacks against digital currency wallets will become more frequent in 2023.

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